

Reproducing Advantage? SES, School Composition, and Access to high-performing upper secondary schools in Estonia.

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Introduction

Educational attainment is shaped not only by individual ability but also by family background, particularly parental education and socioeconomic status (SES) (Brunello & Checchi, 2007; Carneiro & Heckman, 2003; OECD, 2012). Institutional features, such as the presence, timing, and rigidity of tracking, structure students' opportunities and can strengthen existing inequalities (Hanushek & Wössmann, 2006; Brunello & Checchi, 2007). Although tracking aims to align instruction with students' abilities, placement into academic and vocational pathways is strongly influenced by parental resources, aspirations, and familiarity with the education system (Brunello & Checchi, 2007).

This study focuses on Estonia, which has a comprehensive school system without formal tracking during compulsory education. Nevertheless, disparities between schools can reinforce inequalities, as higher-SES families are better positioned to secure access in higher-status educational pathways and more prestigious schools, opportunities that may function as qualitative advantages (Lucas, 2001). Using Estonian registry data, the study examines how family SES and the social composition of the school influence students' likelihood of transitioning into 'academic tracks', which is here operationalized as high-performing upper secondary schools with securer way to higher education (RQ1), whether the effect of family SES has changed over time (RQ2), and whether the effect of family SES varies according to school's social composition (RQ3).

Theoretical framework

A growing body of research highlights the mechanisms through which social background shapes students' transitions within tracked education systems. At the institutional level, middle-class parents actively shape and preserve tracking systems to secure advantageous positions for their children within schools (Useem, 1992; Wells & Serna, 1996). As argued by Brunello and Checchi (2007), better-educated parents draw on greater economic, cultural, and informational resources, which enable them to identify key decision points and guide their children through curricular choices that facilitate higher educational attainment. By contrast, lower-educated parents may encourage aspirations but lack the specific information or strategies to translate them into effective educational decisions. As a result, children of more well educated parents have higher probability to enter academic tracks, while those from less privileged families are often channelled into vocational routes. Tracking therefore reflects not only students' abilities but also broader social mechanisms through which family background shapes educational opportunities.

Tracking presents a trade-off between efficiency and equity. Placing students into more homogeneous classrooms allows for more targeted instruction and may enhance overall performance through peer effects (Minter Hoxby, 2000). However, early selection carries the risk of misallocating students due to imperfect measures of ability (Brunello, Ariga, & Giannini, 2004; Dustmann, 2004). Substantial evidence suggest that early tracking strengthens the influence of parental background on achievement, thereby amplifying pre-existing disparities through peer effects and differentiated curricula (Brunello & Checchi, 2007; Pfeffer, 2008; Horn, 2009; 2013; Van de Werfhorst & Mijs, 2010). These dynamics are reinforced by the social composition of schools: early selection tends to cluster students from similar socioeconomic backgrounds within the same tracks or schools. Schools with higher average SES or parental education foster stronger academic aspirations and higher achievement (Perry & McConney, 2010; Palardy, 2013). Peer effects in such environments can operate independently of students' own individual background, as exposure to more favorable peer environments can enhance both performance and aspirations (Opdenakker & van Damme, 2001; Dumay & Dupriez, 2008). Taken together, these findings indicate that while tracking may offer efficiency gains, it also entails substantial costs in terms of social equity.

The duration and rigidity of tracking are key determinants of educational inequality. Evidence shows that countries that delay tracking or adopt comprehensive schooling systems exhibit relatively weak links between family background and educational outcomes (Brunello & Giannini, 2004; Gorard & Smith, 2004; Le Donné, 2014), whereas early-tracking systems such as Germany or Italy tend to magnify the effects of social origin (Hanushek & Wössmann, 2006; Brunello & Checchi, 2007; Horn, 2009). More generally, highly stratified education systems seem to hinder the equalization of educational opportunities and restrict intergenerational mobility (Pfeffer, 2008; Gamoran and Mare, 1989; Kerckhoff, 1995). By contrast, systems that combine delayed tracking with equitable resource allocation and extended instruction time show greater potential to reduce inequalities (Bellei, 2009; Downey et al., 2004).

High-quality early childhood education (ECE) can serve as an important compensatory tool to mitigate inequalities that emerge before formal schooling (Barnett, 2011; Esping-Andersen, 2008; Sylva, 2014). ECE narrows early skill gaps between advantaged and disadvantaged children, although long-term effects vary (Anderson et al., 2003; Burger, 2010). Cross-national studies link higher preschool enrolment rates with weaker links between family background and children's achievement (Esping-Andersen, 2008; Schütz et al., 2008). The Nordic countries illustrate that universal, high-quality preschool systems help equalize starting conditions for children from different social backgrounds and promote mobility (Esping-Andersen, 2006).

The life course perspective (LCP) highlights that as children gain independence, parents play a decreasing role in shaping their educational trajectories (Müller & Karle, 1993). Accordingly, the influence of social background is expected to be strongest at early transitions and weaker at later stages. Other studies have also shown that the effect of family background declines across successive educational stages (Mare, 1980; Shavit & Blossfeld, 1993). In contrast, the theory of effectively maintained inequality (EMI), developed by Lucas (2001), suggests that socioeconomic advantage persists across both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of education. According to EMI, privileged groups consistently secure advantages—whether through quantitative benefits, such as more years of schooling, or qualitative ones, such as higher-quality educational experiences. When entry to a level of education is restricted, socioeconomically advantaged groups use their resources to secure quantitative access. However, once participation at that level of schooling becomes widespread, these families shift their focus to maintaining advantage through qualitative distinctions, such as placement in higher-status educational tracks and curricula, or more prestigious schools. Based on Lucas (2001) EMI emphasizes the continued reproduction of advantage and that as long as children's social position is shaped by their parents' status traits, those from higher-status backgrounds will obtain better educational opportunities in both quantity and quality. When children's own status characteristics eventually replace those of their parents, these traits assume the same stratifying function, thereby sustaining inequality across generations. Thus, effectively maintained inequality explains how social advantage persists: even as educational participation expands, social background continues to shape the type and quality of education students receive.

Understanding how inequality is reproduced requires attention to the mechanisms and resources that drive this process. Prior research highlights the importance of families' economic and cultural resources in shaping children's educational outcomes (De Graaf et al., 2000). The economic resources hypothesis argues that wealthier families can secure access to higher-quality schooling, thereby increasing their children's chances of pursuing education beyond the compulsory level. Meanwhile, cultural capital is expected to enable children from socially advantaged backgrounds to pursue longer and more successful educational pathways. Parents with substantial cultural resources can cultivate skills and dispositions that facilitate academic achievement and smoother progression through school. Both Bourdieu's (1977) theory of capital and choice-oriented

perspectives identify parental education as a central resource, as highly educated parents are better equipped to provide environments that support learning.

These insights highlight that educational inequality is not the product of any single factor but emerges from the interaction of individual abilities, families, schools and the institutional design of the educational systems. Systems that sort students early and provide limited compensatory support tend to reinforce social gradients, whereas systems that delay selection, promote inclusive schooling, and invest in early childhood education are more effective in leveling initial disparities and promote equality of opportunity (Van de Werfhorst & Mijs, 2010; Hanushek & Wössmann, 2005; Brunello & Checchi, 2007).

Estonia

Although Estonia operates a comprehensive school system without formal tracking during compulsory education, differences between schools may create opportunities for stratification. High-performing upper secondary schools, in particular, may serve as qualitative advantages (Lucas, 2001) that families with higher socioeconomic backgrounds are better positioned to access, thereby reinforcing educational inequalities. Admission to these schools is highly competitive and often involves entrance tests, preschool preparation programs, and substantial parental knowledge of the system – resources that advantaged families are more capable of mobilising (Rosenbaum, Miller, & Krei, 1996). Residential location further reinforces these patterns, as many academically prestigious community schools are located in more expensive neighbourhoods, making them disproportionately accessible to children from affluent families. Although most students continue studying in general upper secondary education, heterogeneity in school performance and peer composition may amplify social background effects on subsequent educational transitions. A recent study by Põder et al. (2023) shows that comprehensive schools in Estonia exhibit considerable variation in the median income of their students' families, with some schools demonstrating stronger income-selectivity at both the upper-secondary and basic school levels. The authors bring as an example Tallinn's well-known G12 elite schools, which are able to select children from affluent families through their admissions process, which includes entrance tests for primary school applicants. They also note that a similar pattern of social selection persists at the upper-secondary level. Thus, in Estonia, educational inequalities may be reproduced through differential access to qualitatively superior educational institutions, enabling advantaged families to secure trajectories that improve their children's future academic and labour market outcomes.

Parental resources also play a decisive role in shaping children's educational attainment in Estonia (Helemäe & Saar, 2016). Research shows that parental education provides a substantial advantage: children of highly educated parents are five times more likely to complete higher education than those whose parents have only basic schooling. Cultural resources, such as the number of books at home, have a persisting positive influence (Helemäe and Saar, 2016), whereas the effect of material resources have remained relatively weak and stable across cohorts (Murd & Saar, 2007).

International assessments indicate that Estonia performs relatively well in mitigating early socioeconomic disparities, ranking close to the OECD average. PISA 2012 results show that social background had a small impact on the learning outcomes of Estonian students (Lindemann, 2013). However, based on the results of the most recent PISA cycle, the influence of students' socioeconomic background on achievement has been increasing (Lindemann, 2023). In addition, language-based stratification introduces a further dimension of inequality that needs to be taken into account. OECD (2013) notes that in many countries, students with an immigrant background or a home language different from the school's language tend to perform worse. In Estonia, where almost all PISA participants are native-born, the language of instruction and the student's home language are stronger predictors of achievement than immigrant status. Lindemann (2013) findings show that mathematics scores differ remarkably by school language: students in Estonian-language schools score an average of 528 points, compared with 496 points in Russian-language schools. Within Estonian-language schools, students who speak Estonian at home outperform those who speak another home language (530 vs. 508 points).

Data, variables and research strategy

The analysis is based on Estonian administrative data covering the years 2011–2024. The primary data source is the Estonian Education Information System (EHIS), which provides individual-level records on educational trajectories across the entire formal education system, from pre-school to higher education. These records were linked with data from several other national registries, including the Population Register, the Census, and Tax and Income databases, enabling the construction of detailed longitudinal profiles of students and their families.

The analytical sample ($N = 85,205$) includes all basic education, which is compulsory education graduates in Estonia from cohorts 2011–2024. After basic education, majority of students continue in a general upper secondary school. The dependent variable captures the transition to 'academic track' by differentiating between the high-performing general upper secondary schools with higher chances to enter higher education versus other general upper secondary schools. We look at the transitions within one year after graduation from basic (compulsory) education (t). Upper secondary school's performance level was defined based on the average academic outcomes of the graduates of that specific high school prior the transition year, more precisely during the period of $t-3$ to $t-1$. The main independent variable of interest is parental socioeconomic status (SES), measured through both parental education and parental income. SES was measured not only at the individual level but also aggregated to the school (class) level.

The analysis applies multilevel regression analysis, with students (Level 1) nested within schools (Level 2) and years (2011-2024) to account for change in time. This structure allows us to account for both individual- and school-level determinants of educational transitions, as well as temporal variation across cohorts. Next to central individual level characteristics of parental SES, the models control also for graduation year, student's gender and student's ethnicity. On school level we

control next to average parental SES of the basic school graduates on the year t-1 also the basic school's study language (or language scheme in case of language immersion schools where subjects are taught both in Estonian and Russian, either at 40/60 or 60/40 ration). The relevant is important also due to the fact that the originally dual-system of Estonian and Russian-language schools has been gradually converted on the upper secondary education level to Estonian-language schools only.

Research questions and hypotheses

Building on the theoretical perspectives on tracking, effectively maintained inequality, and the role of family and school-level resources—together with the Estonian context of comprehensive schooling but pronounced differences in school quality and peer composition—we study how social background continues to shape educational trajectories at the transition to upper secondary education, more precisely to academic track via following research questions and respective hypotheses:

RQ1: How do the socioeconomic status (SES) of the family and the social composition of the school influence students' probability of transitioning to the academic track?

Research on tracked and quasi-tracked systems shows that parental resources strongly shape educational transitions, both through direct support and through parents' ability to identify and act on critical decision points (Brunello & Checchi, 2007; Lucas, 2001). Even in formally comprehensive systems such as Estonia, access to academically prestigious upper secondary schools functions as a qualitative distinction that advantaged families can more easily secure. Theoretical expectations therefore point toward persistent SES gradients in the likelihood of entering the academic track, reinforced by school-level peer environments.

H1a: Students from higher-SES families in terms of parental education have a higher probability of transitioning to the academic track compared to students from lower-SES families.

H1b: Students from higher-SES families in terms of parental income have a higher probability of transitioning to the academic track compared to students from lower-SES families.

H1c: Students attending schools with higher average SES have a higher probability of transitioning to the academic track compared to students in lower-SES schools.

RQ2: Has the effect of family SES on entering the academic track changed over time?

According to the life course perspective, the influence of parental background may weaken as students age (Müller & Karle, 1993). In contrast, the effectively maintained inequality (EMI)

framework suggests that advantaged families preserve relative advantages even when access to education expands, by securing positions in higher-status institutions or tracks (Lucas, 2001). In Estonia, where the share of students continuing in general upper secondary education is high but school quality varies, these mechanisms may intensify over time, especially if competition for prestigious upper secondary schools has grown (partly due to the increase of birth cohort sizes).

H2: The positive effect of family SES on entry into the academic track has strengthened over time.

RQ3: Does the effect of family SES on transition to the academic track vary across schools' socioeconomic composition?

The theoretical literature highlights the role of peer effects and school environments in amplifying or mitigating social background inequalities (Opdenakker & van Damme, 2001; Perry & McConney, 2010). In Estonia, substantial achievement differences between school types—especially between Estonian- and Russian-language schools and between high- and average-performing community schools—may create contexts in which family SES matters differentially. EMI suggests that privileged families benefit more from environments rich in cultural and informational resources, while stratified school composition can reinforce existing inequalities.

H3: The positive effect of family SES on entry into the academic track varies across schools' socioeconomic composition levels: the positive effects are magnified in higher-SES schools.

Findings

The effect of parental SES on transition to academic track

As shown in Model 1, students from higher SES families have a significantly higher probability of entering the academic track (high-performing high schools). This association holds both when SES is operationalized via parents' education (mother and/or father having higher education) or through parental annual log-income. These empirical findings align closely with Brunello and Checchi (2007), who argued that children of more highly educated parents are more likely to enter academic educational tracks. The patterns are also consistent with previous research from Estonia, which demonstrates that parental resources play an important role in shaping children's educational attainment. Helemäe and Saar (2016) found that children of highly educated parents are substantially more likely to complete higher education than those whose parents have only basic schooling. Within the context of our study, it is plausible to expect that students enrolled in the academic track of high-performing upper secondary schools are aspiring to higher education and are more likely to continue to university, further exacerbating educational inequality. While

some earlier studies (Murd & Saar, 2007) showed that the influence of material resources has remained relatively weak but stable across cohorts, our findings indicate that household income is nevertheless an important factor and has a positive effect on children's likelihood of entering academic tracks in terms of high-performing upper secondary schools.

At the individual level, the effect of graduation year is negative and statistically significant, indicating that the probability to enter academic track schools has decreased over time. This could be partly explained by the increase of birth rate in early 2000s, which led to later birth cohorts bigger in size facing 'higher competition' for a relatively fixed number of school places. Another inequality association can be observed regarding the ethnicity of the students – compared to Estonians, Russian, but also other students face greater difficulties in gaining access to academic track in terms of high-performing high schools.

When school-level characteristics are added to the model, the positive effect of family SES on entry into the academic track (i.e. high-performing) schools becomes smaller but remains statistically significant. Furthermore, the analyses reveal a positive school-level effect – students from schools with higher average parental SES level exhibit a higher probability to enter academic track. This pattern reflects the mechanisms described in prior studies, which show that schools with more socioeconomically advantaged student composition tend to provide learning environments that foster stronger academic performance (Burger, 2016; Perry & McConney, 2010) and increase students' chances of progressing to more academically demanding pathways (Palardy, 2013). Similarly, Põder et al. (2023) demonstrate that socioeconomically advantaged schools, such as Tallinn's G12 elite schools, select and concentrate students from higher income families, thereby creating more homogeneous and supportive learning environments. Thus, our results support the view that both individual- and school-level socioeconomic advantages work together to shape more prestigious educational trajectories, despite the comprehensive school model of Estonia.

Table 1 The effect of parental SES on entry to academic track, log-coefficients

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Individual level factors:</i>				
Mother's higher education	0.372***	0.371***	0.115**	-0.609
Father's higher education	0.375***	0.374***	0.185***	-0.694
Parents' (joint) annual log-income	0.117***	0.111***	0.060**	-0.962***
Year of graduating basic school (centered)	-0.266***	-0.285***	-0.367***	-0.289***
Female	0.162***	0.162***	0.160***	0.161***
<i>Ethnicity (Ref: Estonian)</i>				
Other	-0.309***	-0.295***	-0.298***	-0.291***
Russian	-0.225***	-0.211***	-0.213***	-0.210***
<i>School level factors:</i>				
Basic school graduates' parents' mean income		0.257***	0.257***	-0.816***
<i>School language (Ref: Estonian)</i>				
Estonian (language immersion)		-0.138	-0.140	-0.136
Russian		-0.210*	-0.215*	-0.214*
Other		1.044	0.962	1.082
Mother's higher education*Graduation year			0.031***	
Father's higher education*Graduation year			0.021***	
Parents' joint annual log-income*Graduation year			0.006**	
Mother's higher education*School: parents' mean log-income				0.098**
Father's higher education* School: parents' mean log-income				0.104**
Individual: parents' log-income*School: parents' mean log-income				0.107***
Constant	534.678*** (2.390)	-2.023*** (0.542)	-1.360** (0.579)	8.734*** (1.959)
Observations	85,205	85,205	85,205	85,205
Log Likelihood	-42,459.590	-42,447.780	-42,410.440	-42,416.590
Akaike Inf. Crit.	84,937.170	84,921.560	84,852.880	84,865.190
Bayesian Inf. Crit.	85,021.350	85,043.150	85,002.530	85,014.830
Note:	* p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01			

Source: Authors' calculations based on Estonian Education Information System + additional administrative data

At the school level, it should also be pointed out that students from Russian-language basic schools have a significantly lower probability of entering academic track schools. One contributing factor may be that attending schools where instruction is partly or predominantly in Russian limits students' opportunities to develop strong academic proficiency in Estonian language. This can negatively affect their performance on standardized assessments and entrance examinations that

are conducted in Estonian. Since admission to high-performing academic-track schools is strongly merit-based, these accumulated language-related disadvantages reduce minority students' chances of being selected. Lindemann (2013) identified substantial performance gaps related to both school language and home language. Thus, language functions as a structural barrier contributing to the underrepresentation of Russian-speaking and other minority students in the highest-performing segments of the upper-secondary system.

The temporal change in the effect of family SES in entry to academic track

Our second research question (and respectively the hypothesis H2) posed that the effect of family SES on educational opportunities has changed in time. More precisely, we expected the positive effect become bigger/stonger in time. The interaction effects between parental SES and time (Figure 1 based on Model 3 in Table 1) indicate that while transition probability to academic track has increased in time for all students, the parental education makes still a difference: both in case of father's and mother's education, having high educated parent increases the probability to enter significantly. Moreover so, the positive effect of parental higher education increases in time and the difference/increase is statistically significant. In other words, having higher educated mother and/or father compared to having parent(s) with lower educational level has become even more crucial for (academic) success in post-compulsory education.

Figure 1 Predicted probabilities for entering academic track by parent's education and year of graduation

Source: Authors' calculations based on Estonian Education Information System + additional administrative data; Model 3 in Table 1

The same trend and association hold true also for the effect of household income (Figure 2 based on model 3 in Table 1) - not only does higher parental income relate to higher chances to enter

academic track, but the difference between different income levels¹ grows bigger in time and respectively the effect of parental income becomes stronger in time, whereas the change/increase is statistically significant. This means that families with SES advantage and respectively greater cultural and economic resources have been more recently increasingly able to convert these advantages into more desirable educational pathways for their children.

Figure 2 Predicted probabilities for entering academic track by parental mean income level

Source: Authors’ calculations based on Estonian Education Information System + additional administrative data; Model 3 in Table 1

The potential accumulation of resources on individual and school level

Individual and school level (higher) SES seem also to ‘magnify’ one another. As shown on Figure 3 (based on Model 4 in Table 1), the higher the average parental income on school level, the higher is on average the probability to enter in academic track (high-achieving) high schools. Although the students from different family background tend to benefit from higher school SES level, students with higher educated mother and/or father benefit clearly more – not only are their transition probabilities on average higher, the ‘advantage’ becomes bigger the higher is the school level average parental SES. The differentiating (interaction) effect is statistically significant.

¹ In order to present the interactions of a plot, we differentiate between three parental income categories: -1 SD below mean; mean, +1SD above the mean

Figure 3 Predicted probabilities for entering academic track by parent's education and school-level SES

Source: Authors' calculations based on Estonian Education Information System + additional administrative data; Model 4 in Table 1

The same trend appears also when looking at the interaction between household and school level SES in terms of parental income. On average, students from higher SES-level schools have higher probabilities to transit to academic track high schools. However, the chances differ still by household income level – the higher the mean household income level, the higher the probability to continue in academically inclined high schools, whereas the difference between income groups increases when school-level SES increases. In other words, the students from economically better off families benefit more from (income-based) high-SES school environment when it comes to educational trajectories.

Figure 4 Predicted probabilities for entering academic track by household and school-level parental income

Discussion

This study examined how social background continues to structure students' transitions to the academic track of upper secondary education in Estonia, a formally comprehensive system where no institutional tracking is implemented during basic schooling. Drawing on theories of effectively maintained inequality (EMI), parental resource mechanisms, and peer composition effects, as well as on known patterns of stratification within the Estonian school system, we addressed three research questions concerning (1) individual and school-level SES effects on academic track entry, (2) temporal change in these effects, and (3) the extent to which family SES interacts with the socioeconomic composition of schools. The findings provide consistent evidence that educational inequality remains pronounced and, in some cases, has intensified over time.

The first research question asked how family socioeconomic status and the socioeconomic composition of schools shape students' probability of entering the academic track. The results offer strong support for all three hypotheses (H1a–H1c). Consistent with H1a, students whose parents have higher education exhibit markedly higher probabilities of entering academic-track upper secondary schools than their peers from less educated families. This pattern aligns with earlier findings in Estonia (Helemäe & Saar, 2016) and with international research demonstrating that parents' cultural and informational resources shape children's ability to navigate educational

decision points (Brunello & Checchi, 2007; Lucas, 2001). Likewise, H1b is confirmed: parental log-income significantly increases the likelihood of transitioning to the academic track. Even though prior Estonian research suggested only modest long-term effects of material resources (Murd & Saar, 2007), the present analyses show that economic resources remain an important driver of educational advantage. Importantly, also H1c is supported by our findings. School-level socioeconomic composition exerts an independent, positive effect on students' academic-track entry. Students attending schools with higher average parental SES have substantially better chances of obtaining a place in high-performing upper secondary schools. This result aligns with Põder et al. (2023) findings, who show that Estonian comprehensive schools differ significantly based on the median income of students' families and that some elite schools tend to concentrate children from higher-income families. This result is consistent with research demonstrating that socioeconomic peer environments promote stronger academic performance and higher educational aspirations (Perry & McConney, 2010; Palardy, 2013). Even within Estonia's comprehensive model, advantaged school environments appear to confer cumulative benefits — reinforcing rather than attenuating inequalities produced by family background.

These findings suggest that Estonia's comprehensive schooling structure does not fully eliminate the qualitative differentiation of educational opportunities. Instead, access to higher-status institutions at the upper-secondary level functions as a selective gate where social background continues to shape outcomes.

A further inequality dimension emerges with respect to language. Students from Russian-language basic schools, as well as those from other linguistic minority backgrounds, demonstrate significantly lower transition probabilities compared to Estonian-speaking peers. This is consistent with earlier evidence of large performance gaps between school language groups (Lindemann, 2013) and suggests that linguistic stratification acts as a structural barrier that compounds socioeconomic disadvantage.

The second research question examined whether the influence of family SES on academic-track entry has changed across cohorts. The findings provide clear support for H2: the positive effect of family SES has strengthened over time. Interaction analyses showed that while transitions into academic-track schools have become more selective overall, the advantage enjoyed by students from higher-SES families — whether measured by parental education or income — has grown larger for more recent cohorts. Both parental education and household income increasingly differentiate students' opportunities to access prestigious academic pathways. The fact that these interactions are statistically significant suggests a meaningful and systematic deepening of socioeconomic inequality. Several contextual factors can help explain this trend. First, the increase in birth cohort sizes in the early 2000s intensified competition for a largely fixed supply of places in academically oriented upper secondary schools. Second, EMI theory emphasizes that advantaged families mobilize cultural, informational, and financial resources to maintain their children's relative position as competition rises (Lucas, 2001). The empirical pattern observed here

— widening gaps over time — is fully consistent with this mechanism. Thus, rather than converging or stabilizing across cohorts, socioeconomic disparities in educational trajectories in Estonia appear to be intensifying, reinforcing the intergenerational reproduction of advantage.

The third research question focused on whether the effect of family SES varies across schools' socioeconomic composition. The findings confirm H3. Across parental education and parental income measures, students benefit from attending higher-SES schools. However, the magnitude of this benefit differs markedly by family background. Higher-SES students not only start from a more advantageous position; their advantage increases as school-level SES rises. This indicates a magnification effect: high-SES families are best positioned to capitalize on the enabling opportunities offered by socioeconomically advantaged school environments. These results resonate strongly with explanations rooted in EMI and peer effects. Higher-SES schools concentrate students whose families possess greater cultural and material resources, generating academically oriented peer climates and school cultures. Students from already advantaged backgrounds are better equipped to leverage such environments, resulting in cumulative benefits across both individual and contextual dimensions of SES. Conversely, students from lower-SES households do benefit from attending higher-status schools but to a much lesser degree. This suggests that contextual advantages cannot fully compensate for disadvantages rooted in family resources — leading to widening relative disparities in selective educational transitions.

Taken together, the results paint a consistent and robust picture: despite Estonia's comprehensive school structure and historically modest SES gradients in student achievement, inequalities in transition to the academic track persist and appear to be growing. Family SES powerfully shapes educational opportunities, and this influence not only remains strong over time but, in several respects, is becoming more pronounced. Furthermore, school-level socioeconomic composition does not mitigate these disparities; instead, it interacts with family resources in ways that reinforce cumulative inequality. These findings have important policy implications. They suggest that the pathway to high-status upper secondary education — a key gateway to higher education — is increasingly stratified. As competition for elite school places rises, families with greater cultural and economic capital appear ever more capable of converting their advantages into educational success. This dynamic threatens to undermine the egalitarian goals of Estonia's comprehensive school system and challenges assumptions that delayed tracking alone is sufficient to ensure equity. Strengthening support for lower-SES students, improving language support for minority-language pupils, and reducing between-school differences may therefore be necessary steps to counteract the growing polarization in educational trajectories.

While the study provides important insights into the mechanisms through which family and school-level socioeconomic resources shape students' transitions to the academic track, several limitations must be acknowledged. These limitations relate both to data availability and to the analytical choices inherent in modelling selective educational transitions. The most consequential limitation concerns the (current) absence of direct measures of students' academic ability or prior academic

achievement. Because the current administrative dataset does not yet include students' exam results, the analysis cannot disentangle the extent to which transitions to high-performing upper secondary schools reflect differences in academic performance versus differences in social background. Prior research shows that academic achievement is strongly associated with socioeconomic status (Sirin, 2005), and high-performing schools in Estonia rely heavily on merit-based admission criteria. Without controlling for achievement, the estimated effects of parental education and income likely overstate the independent influence of family SES, capturing both direct socioeconomic effects and those mediated by performance differences accumulated throughout basic school.

A related limitation is that the study does not account for students' educational aspirations or parental involvement in school choice processes, both of which may intervene between family background and transition outcomes. Highly educated or higher-income parents may be more active in navigating application procedures, preparing their children for entrance exams, or strategically choosing schools. These mechanisms cannot be observed in the available administrative data but may contribute to systematic SES differences in academic-track access.

Another constraint concerns the measurement of school-level socioeconomic composition. Although average parental income at the school level serves as a useful proxy for school-SES environments, it does not fully capture other dimensions of school quality — such as teacher characteristics, resource allocation, extracurricular supports, or informal school cultures — that may shape students' educational trajectories. Similarly, unobserved school-level factors, such as principals' selection practices or local competition between schools, may play a role but remain unmeasured.

The analysis also relies on observational data, which limits causal inference. While multilevel modelling helps account for clustering within schools and controls for a range of demographic characteristics, unobserved confounders (e.g., parental motivations, school choice strategies) may bias estimates. Moreover, although we examine temporal changes in SES effects, the model does not include detailed policy or institutional changes that might help explain cohort-specific developments.

Despite these limitations, the analyses offer robust evidence of widening socioeconomic disparities in access to the academic track. Future research incorporating achievement data, more detailed school characteristics, or longitudinal designs would help clarify the pathways through which family and school resources jointly shape students' educational trajectories.

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